

Topic: The gender discrimination of childhood education at Ratnanagar Municipality in Nepal

Author: Dr. Basanta Prasad Adhikari [Research Head, Oxford College of Engineering and Management, Nawalpur, Nepal].

Email: Adhikari_bp@ymail.com Ph: 009779865206991

Abstract

The primary objective of this study was to examine the perceptions of the parents of Chitwan District on their preferences to send their sons at institutionalized schools and daughters at community schools. This study has applied the qualitative research approach where the qualitative interview along with the Semi-structured interview was used to collect data from the fifteen sample interviewees of family heads at Ratnanagar Chitwan of Nepal. The interviewees were selected purposively. The previous studies reveal that Nepalese society is still male dominated to educate their children. The results show that out of fifteen interviewees, seven were female and eight were male household's head. The results show that the parents had greater preference to send their sons at institutionalized schools and daughters at community schools signifying that their sons were enrolled at institutionalized schools and daughters at community schools. The results also indicate that parents were found more willing to spend a large amount of their income for son's education but often hesitate to spend their income on their daughters' education. The results also show that sons were "god's gift and mentally and politically strong by nature" and insisted on sons' preference signifying for their quality education via expensive institutionalized schools. The results disclosed that highly educated girls had violated the Nepalese social norms and ritual cultures and also concluded that keeping a girl uneducated had the potential to preserve traditional values, particularly in reference to patriarchal hierarchy. The implication of this study will be beneficial to the policy makers to focus on gender equality in the childhood education in Nepal. The limitations of this study were limited number of interviewees involved in the study and generalization of the finding to the similar context.

Keywords: Preference, discrimination, childhood education, sons and daughters, interviewees.

1 Introduction:

“Gender discrimination is one of the major drawbacks in Nepalese culture”.

Nepal is an underdeveloped country which is situated between India and China. The country extends to 1,47,181 square kilometres. Nepal presents dismal female literacy rates. Within the SAARC region, Nepal has the lowest female literacy rate. The literacy level of people above six years is 54 percent. Divided by gender, men have a literacy rate of 65 percent and women only 42.5 percent (Central Bureau of Statistics, Nepal, 2003). Nepal has already made commitment of an international slogan of free quality school education to all children but the current practice on childhood education is still problematic in Nepal (Caddell, 2007). It is accepted that poor performance of public schools increases the emergence of institutionalized schools rapidly as an alternative. As a consequence, a dual school system has taken place in Nepal. Due to unaffordable cost for poor and inaccessibility for remote areas children, a burning issue of equity arises in the Nepalese education sector. The school system is producing two social classes of children, which is the antithesis of the goal of education (Department of Education, 2009).

Koolwal (2007, p.881) states the following in reference to the gender preference in low income countries. *“Son preference is an enduring phenomenon in many low-income countries, particularly Asia, North Africa, and the Middle East”.*

Male preference is still debatable in the Nepalese society. The community of Nepal has already announced the implementation of equal opportunity for both male and female, but the Nepalese societies still believe that men are the pillars of every family to manage economic activities. Traditional Nepalese concepts of gender roles prioritize male education, while relegating women to household works (Central Bureau of Statistics, Nepal, 2003).

“Men are breadwinners; women are homemakers” (Ho & Lam, 2014, p.498).

The net enrolment rate for boys stands at 86 percent and for girls, 74.6 percent. This clearly shows gender disparity among boys and girls in education as in other sectors of Nepalese society. Moreover, there are two types of Pre-Primary, Primary, and Lower Secondary Schools in Nepal. People spend 200 to 500 EURO to educate sons in institutionalized schools which directly impacts their annual saving. If the quality of education in community schools improves, it is believed that the rate of gender discrimination may be minimized (Koirala, 2015). Community and institutionalized schools also display gaps in quality of guardian

supervision. Institutionalized school guardians are thought to be stricter, as the students are paying for attendance. Unfortunately, people still send their sons to the institutionalized schools while sending their daughters to community schools. There are currently no policies in place to create gender equality in enrolment in institutionalized schools (Department of Education, 2009). Nepalese policy makers have to open their eyes open to improve the quality of education so that parents may believe community schools and send their sons and daughter in community schools (Khanal, 2018). Free quality school education to all children is an international slogan of education and Nepal has made commitment to receive that goals. The community has been focusing to improve the rate of children' enrollment in Nepalese public schools, however; the outcomes of the community 's efforts and budget are not quantifiable. More, importantly, the quality of education in public schools is not satisfactory due to the political intervention at public sector schools (Shiwakoti et al, 2004). The objective of this study was to find the number of families who have sent their sons to institutionalized schools and girls to community schools in Ratnanagar Municipality. Furthermore, it also aims to evaluate why the sons are sent to institutionalized schools and daughters are send to community schools and are compelled to engage at indoor and outdoor household activities. The next objective was also to conduct the qualitative interviews with fifteen sample family heads to understand their views of gender discrimination on childhood education at Ratnanagar Municipality at Chitwan District in Nepal.

2. Qualitative Research Approach

This study has used the qualitative research approach because it provides an in-depth description and understanding of the human experience. More importantly, description and understanding of human phenomena, human interaction, or human discourse are embedded in qualitative research philosophy (Cohen, Manion, Morrison, 2007). Bergman, (2009) states that "Qualitative researchers stress the socially constructed nature of reality, the intimate relationship between the researcher and what is studied, and the situational constraints that shape inquiry. Such researchers emphasize the value-laden nature of inquiry. They seek answers to questions that stress how social experience is created and given meaning (p. 2).

Qualitative researchers stress the socially constructed nature of reality, the intimate relationship between the researcher and what is studied, and the situational constraints that shape inquiry. Such researchers emphasize the value-laden nature of inquiry. They seek answers to questions that stress how social experience is created and given meaning (Bergman, 2009).

Cohen et al (2007) notes that “Normative researchers attempt to devise general theories of human behaviour and to validate them through the use of increasingly complex research methodologies, which some believe, push them further from the experience and understanding of the everyday world and into the world of abstraction” (p.22). Qualitative researchers believe that social reality can be constructed by the human interaction collectively which is external to the actor and manifest in society, and its institutions and its organization (Lune & Berg, 2018).

2.1 Interviews

This study had used semi-structured interviews to collect data from the fifteen sample households’ heads because this instrument is a flexible tool for data collection, enabling multi-sensory channels can be used for example, verbal, non-verbal, spoken and heard (Clough & Nutbrown, 2007). An interview is also a popular research method to collect data in a case study research which is also a key method to collect information and transfer it to the researcher, a transaction which inevitably has bias. This needs to be identified and controlled by the researchers to share many features of teacher attrition and retention (Onwuegbuzie & Leech, 2009). The main purposes of the interview were to evaluate parents’ perception in some respect of his/her children sent to institutionalized and community schools, to grab sample parents’ opinion on sons’ preference for the quality education (Opie, 2004). Conceptions of interview are rooted in three different parts. Firstly, one is that of an interview means of pure information transfer from the interviewees to the interviewers which is appeared to be widely held, a second concept of interview is that of a transaction which inevitably has bias that needs to be identified and controlled. The third conception of the interview sees as an encounter necessarily sharing many of the features of everyday life experience (Lichtman, 2006). Out of fifteen interviewees, seven were female and eight were male household’s head.

2.2 Data analysis

This study has used the content analysis because the nature of this study is tradition and cultural issue of our Society. Content analysis is one of the popular data analysis methods of educational research because it facilitates the researcher for the direct communication through texts and transcripts and gets central facet of social interaction (Cohen et al, 2007). There are seven steps in the content analysis. The first, second, third, fourth, fifth, sixth, and seventh steps of analysis are to define the research questions; know the sample population; to know the included sample; define the context of the generation of the document and the unit of analysis; decide the codes to use in the analysis and to construct the categories for data analysis (Lichtman, 2006).

3. Radiality and validity of the qualitative findings

The external validity and internal validity are the issue of my research study where internal validity indicates the soundness or the quality of the research and external validity is rooted in the degree of "generalizability which means whether the outcomes or results of the study are applicable to a population or not (Bilali, 2014). Validity is the unavoidable prerequisite for qualitative research. Additionally, validity is deeply rooted in a particular research instrument which should measure what it purposes to measure. The same requirement was essential for this study (Cohen et al., 2007). In the qualitative interview's data, validity was discussed through the honesty of interviewees because all the interviewees were feeling happy and seemed to deliver the factual data, perception and opinions during the interview time. The words used for the validity of the qualitative study are credibility, transferability, conformability and dependability. The truth value of this study signifies the credibility of qualitative research because the interpretations of the transcribed data were finalized by the same interviewees of the qualitative study (Lichtman, 2006). Similarly, the validity of this study also rooted in the depth, richness and space of the data attained the participant method, the degree of triangulation and the objectivity of the study. The next step of the reliability of this study is embedded in a fit between what was recorded during the interview time and what actually occurred in the natural setting that was being carefully researched which signifies the transferability of qualitative approach because the findings will fit samples and settings beyond the current research (Opie, 2004). More importantly, the samples were selected from fifteen household heads based on their age, income level and educational qualification and gender ration who had really sent their sons in institutionalized schools and daughter in community schools (Cohen et al. 2007).

It was concluded that validity is based on understate or overstate the true value of the attitude and perceptions of household heads on the preference of sons and daughters for their primary education (Cohen et al., 2007). The researcher of this study had regularly and systematically produced descriptions, records, and reflections with the intention of recording the household heads perceptions on their gender preference and interactions as accurately and thoroughly as possible in order to increase the credibility and accuracy of the qualitative data. Additionally, the qualitative questions were purely based on the current practices of gender discrimination in childhood education occurring at school sector in Nepal because this researcher is also working in the school sector management. Dependability of the qualitative study was met by the stability of the findings and the ability to track variance in the data over time (Humphrey,

2014). Therefore, the confirmability of the qualitative study was evidenced by other household heads who were not participated in the current research because this study had presented the transcribed data to six selected sample households head to know their perceptions after interpretation of the qualitative interview data who had the same characteristics of the previous sample households heads (Long & Johnson, 2000). Again, credibility of research needs authors to prove familiarity with the topic and holding adequate data to make claims, linking a strong logical between explanations and categories, and materials that permit others to choose whether they agree with the claims. Transferability is a method of re-thinking the idea of generalizability in the outline of Lincoln and Guba's (1985). The dependability of the qualitative research was deeply rooted in my data measurement standard where this researcher really wanted to measure the intention of parents to send their children in two different nature schools. The current research instruments also measured the same as this study intended to measure so that the dependability of the qualitative study was supported (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2011). The data collection and subsequent analysis were conducted according to Creswell & Plano Clark (2011) guidelines for the effective conduct of qualitative research. To address the concern that household heads might not be completely open with the researcher during interviews due to various social or professional concerns. It was collected interview data without identifying characteristics attached to participants' responses. It was then compared the first-hand accounts and personal interviews in order to improve the quality and accuracy of qualitative data analysis. Next, it was compared the qualitative data to the written reports to guarantee the reliability, credibility and validity of the qualitative findings (Cohen et al, 2007).

3. RESULTS

Parents still believe that the sons will look after them in their old age. Interviewees said that they can see their sons at institutionalized schools look smarter than girls at community schools. This scenario also signifies that parents prefer quality education for their sons so that boys' enrolment in the institutionalized schools was found higher than girls' enrolment in the community schools (Simkhdawa et al, 2004). Recorded transcribed interview data were analysed through content analysis, a process which summarises written, spoken or visual communication quantitatively. Transcripts were reviewed for their core concepts or themes. Those themes are defined below as direct quotes and followed by discussion (Cohen et al, 2013). Content analysis has been used to ask into gender-based discrimination in childhood education. Content analysis provides an efficient way to code responses to open-ended questions and assess the deeper meaning. It is usually less subjective, format tends to be easier

to code than content which has been used as a research methodology for understanding the reasons of discrimination on childhood education in Nepal because the content analysis is an appropriate data analysis method to analyze the data of traditional cultural (Dumay & Cai, 2014).

3.1 The first main content

I believe that my son will look after me when I will be grown in older age.

Male dominated family systems provide very little scope for the female to assert their identity. They are marginalized from economic and social opportunities due to the illiteracy, poverty and conservative social prohibitions (Dixit, 2011). The results show that the first family head said that he had sent his son to institutionalized school and daughter to a community school. He believed that his daughters would go to the next family after marriage. He expected his son to stay with him in the same family and look after him as they both grew older age. The first household head further added that he could not be sure that his daughters would support him and his wife in the future. The literature of the Nepalese society to male population also supported the views of the first interviewee (Chopra, 2012). The first interviewee also commented that he would need his son after his death for the religious work according to Nepalese culture. There is a Nepalese traditional thought that after the death of their parents, sons need to be seated to religious work for thirteen days. This study has supported the previous findings of Camilli et al. (2010) because both studies found that societal expectations for filial support reinforce gender-based discrimination in education in Nepal.

One of the interviewees, strongly argued that his daughters must not be highly educated. He suggested that if his daughters attained high levels of education, they would marry without his permission or guidance. It is notable that there is still strong culture for the arrange marriage and love marriage is regarded as a bad culture in the Nepalese society (Dixit, 2011). However, trends in a more modern Nepali society are moving towards rejecting the traditional thoughts of male-dominated families towards the belief that both sons and daughters are of equal importance in a family. The results also show the decimation in the childhood education in Nepal because the first interviewee disclosed his thoughts, he had sent his daughter at a community school and two sons in institutionalized schools for their education. It is important to note that sending children to institutionalize schools in Nepal depicts biases for the childhood education. The results show that parents are more willing to spend a large amount of their income for son's education but often hesitate to spend their income on their daughters' education (Chopra, 2012). This study supported the previous research of Ho and Lam (2014)

because both previous and current studies found that the Nepalese society is still male-dominated, and they still believe that “Men are breadwinners; women are homemakers”.

3.2 The second main content

Males are physically strong, and they can manage the whole family so that they should be more educated. Therefore, I decided to send my son to institutionalized school for the better education.

The third interviewee was belonged to a marginalized Nepali ethnic group which is called Chepang. There were two children in that family where their mother had done a very lower level income job and earns very little money. However, she has sent her son to institutionalized school and daughter to a community school. She cares of said that that education quality was objectively poor and there were no proper children at community schools. The results of fifteen interviewees show that girls were physically, mentally and politically weak, so sons were preferred for highly educating rather than daughters. They further argued that “Sons are god’s gift and mentally and politically strong by nature” and insisted on sons’ preference signifying for their quality education via expensive institutionalized schools. The results also highlighted that a very few sampled parents believe and act on the belief that sons and daughters are of equal importance for the Nepalese family and should be provided equal opportunities. One of the interviewees, remarkably noted “I would not have preferred these three daughters if my wife had given me a son in her first birth.” This kind of thought underlies and has supported the gender inequality in childhood education in Nepalese society. This study has supported the previous study of Chopra (2012) because both studies noted a common theme that males are stronger than females as well as more responsible for caring for their parents so that sons should be more educated and deliver quality education to care their parents in the old age.

3.3 The third content: *I sent my daughters to a community school because they will marry and go to their new homes.*

The qualitative interviews conducted with fifteen families’ heads found that parents were not ready to spend more money on their daughter’s education. During the interview interviewees concluded that daughters would go to their new homes after their marriage so that it would be worthless to spend for them. They further disclose that their sons would stay with them all the time so they would prefer high and quality education for them, not for their daughters. One of the family heads as an interviewee argued remarkably that educating the girls is to spoil our society because highly educated girls violate their Nepalese social norms and ritual cultures. They perceived that keeping a girl uneducated had the potential to preserve traditional values, particularly in reference to patriarchal hierarchy. The results found that the arranged marriage

was a source of social capital for Nepalese families. It is an opportunity for parents to determine the family that will combine with their own family. Losing control over this aspect of their daughter's lives highlights, often negatively, shifting values and power structures. The third interviewee clearly gave his strong voices that daughters must not be educated because high quality girls do not respect the social norms. This study has supported the previous findings of Ho and Lam (2014) because the previous and current studies have found that there was a shared understanding that highly educated girls prefer "love marriages" and avoid arranged marriage signifying the culture damage.

3.4 The fourth statement: *I have sent my sons to institutionalized school because my society is male dominated.*

Out of fifteen family heads, ten of them said that they had sent their sons to institutionalized schools because their neighbours had sent their sons to institutionalized schools which had created them social pressure to do the same as their neighbours had done. But other five strongly disclosed that they preferred to send their children to institutionalized schools for the quality education in the hope of earning good money in future so that they would support them. One of the interviewees strongly argued that sons were god's gift so that he should care and educate more than daughters so that they would be supported by their sons in the heaven after the death of them. This study has supported the study of Dixit (2011) because both previous and current studies found that the Nepalese society was deeply rooted in male-dominated society. They interviewees believed that sons would bring a large amount of cash or prestigious physical materials after their marriage from their father-in-law's house. The other contents content was same as the previous analysed contents so that they were excluded from this discussion.

3.5 Graphic and statistical presentation of the proportion of daughters and sons in both institutionalized and private schools

This researcher visited fifteen institutionalized schools and fifteen community schools. A brief discussion on the enrollment of boys and girls in institutionalized and community schools.

Figure 1

The figure 1 clearly signifies that a large number of girls had gone to the community schools, and a large number of boys had gone to institutionalized schools in Ratnanagar Municipality. This enrollment variation between girls and boys in two different nature schools signifying the discrimination of childhood education in Nepal. This graphic presentation has supported the results of this qualitative study.

Summary of the findings

The interviewees explored by the fifteen interviewees' views on childhood education signify that daughters have to go to their new homes and can't play a crucial role of caring for their parents. Additionally, the results show that the economic activities and values they can add to a household will only benefit the new home. This study supported the previous study of Dhoaj (2013) because both previous and the current study have summarized that parents did not believe their daughters so that they sent them to community schools. They preferred to send their sons in institutionalized schools thinking that they were more likely to depend on sons for support in old age. The results importantly show that the majority of parents had decided to send their daughters to community schools because they believe that regardless of education women will be incapable of attaining high paying employment, limiting their economic contribution to the families. Conversely, the majority of parents wish to send their sons to the institutionalized schools, as the earlier interviewees concluded, because sons require the quality education that will promote the economic prosperity of the home, enabling them to manage their families. The discussion was largely based on the comparison of the enrollment of boys and girls in

institutionalized versus community school, situated at Ratnanagar Chitwan Nepal. The data presented in the histograms (see in the Figure 1) signify the ratio of boys and girls in each class. The enrollment ratio of girls and boys in institutionalized schools and community schools have shown that a large number of girls have gone to the community schools and the large number of boys have gone to the institutionalized schools. The proportion of girls enrolled in community versus institutionalized schools is larger in comparison to the proportion of boys. This suggest a gender imbalance of students' enrollment in childhood education in Ratnanagar, Chitwan District Nepal. The ratio of boys and girls who go to the community and institutionalized schools reflects that parents desire to send their daughters at the community schools and sons at the institutionalized schools. The results show that the greater number of girls' enrolment in community schools and a greater number of boys' enrolment in the institutionalized schools' points toward discrimination of childhood education in Nepal. When taken together with the qualitative data, the imbalance in enrollment clearly exists within a context that dismisses the potential importance and impact of female education.

4. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

The objective of this study was to examine the perceptions of household heads for their preference to educate their children. The results highlighted that childhood education in Nepal is still biased to male population. The results also concluded that while advancements have been made to provide free education through community schools, this education is widely considered to be insufficient in comparison to the education provided institutionalized schools. The results also disclosed that in comparison to institutionalized schools, community schools are highly funded but provide a poorer quality of education. Despite this, a large number of girls are enrolled in community schools, while their brothers receive an opportunity to get quality, or at least better education in institutionalized schools. This disparity can be traced back to a history of gender-based marginalization in the Nepalese society. This study was conducted at Ratnanagar Municipality, Chitwan in Nepal. Fifteen family heads were interviewed to know the thoughts of family heads why parents discriminate their children in childhood education. This study clearly found that sons were sent to institutionalized schools in the hope of getting support from their sons when parents get older and physically weak. This research also found that parents send their sons to institutionalized schools for quality education because they believe that sons can manage all household economic activities and are authorized to do all spiritual activities, for example, the activities after the death of their parents. According to traditional culture, girls are banned to do spiritual work as male population do. More significantly, parents send their daughters to the community schools because they still

think that girls go to their new homes after their marriage and cannot care their parents when they get older. The results have concluded that traditional spiritual thoughts are the key influencing deeply rooted factors signifying that childhood education is still a debatable issue in the Nepalese societies because parents still discriminate their children while sending them to schools. Finally, the results have concluded that males are physically, mentally and politically strong so that parents send their sons to high quality schools and girls to low quality schools. In one hand, Nepalese education is free and compulsory up to the secondary level, but the institutionalized schools are not free of costs. More significantly, there is dual educational policy for the free and compulsory education which creates disputes between two different nature schools in Nepal. The main reason of using qualitative method was the nature of the research phenomenon because qualitative method is very appropriate to collect the data on cultural and traditional thoughts. More importantly, most of the interviewees had very limited education signifying that they cannot complete the survey questionnaires. The implication of this study will be beneficial for the policy makers of local, regional and national level to formulate new educational policy to minimize the gender discrimination in childhood education. The limitations of this study were limited number of interviewees involved in the study and generalization of the results in the similar context.

REFERENCES:

- Bergman, M. (2009). *Advances in mixed methods research*. Los Angeles, Calif.: Sage.
- Bilali, O. (2014). The Teacher Anxiety Scale: The Study of Validity and Reliability. *Journal of Educational and Social Research*. doi: 10.5901/jesr.2014.v4n2p90
- Caddell M, 2007. Institutionalized Schools and Political Conflict in Nepal in P. Walford (ed.) *Institutionalized Schooling in Less Economically Developed Countries: Asian and African Perspectives*. Oxford: Symposium Books.
- Camilli, G., S. Vargas, S. Ryan, and S. Barnett (2010). Meta-analysis of the effects of early education interventions on cognitive and social development. *Teachers*.
- Central Bureau of Statistics, Nepal (2003). *Population monograph of Nepal*, Kathmandu, Nepal.
- Chopra, N, 2012. A study of early childhood education programmes in Delhi, India, *International Journal of Early Years Education*, 20:2, 159-174.
- Clough, P., & Nutbrown, C. (2007). *A student's guide to methodology*. London: SAGE Publications.